

The background of the cover features an aerial photograph of a river winding through a dry, brown landscape. The river is a vibrant blue-green color. In the bottom right corner, there is a dark blue overlay with white, glowing lines and dots, resembling a data visualization or a network map. The text is positioned on the right side of the cover.

International Scientific and Practical Conference

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

PROCEEDINGS
(Conference Proceedings)

May 19, 2026

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

WICAR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

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International Scientific and Practical Conference -2026

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference innovative approaches to water resource management in arid regions in the context of climate change on May 19, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The conference aims to discuss key issues of effective water resource management in arid regions under climate change, develop and apply innovative approaches and mathematical and computational modeling methods, share recent research results and practical experience, and strengthen international academic cooperation in this field.

Key Themes of the Conference:

1. Water Diplomacy and Integrated Approaches in International Relation: Interdisciplinary Approaches to Sustainable Development, Communication and Global Security

- Issues of systemic analysis in international relations and world politics in the context of water diplomacy
- Economic, environmental and energy aspects of sustainable development
- Systemic approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

2. Mathematical and computer modeling of optimal water resources management under climate change

- Optimal water resource management under climate change
- Modeling water resource dynamics and climate variability
- Methods of applied and computational mathematics in irrigation system modeling.

3. Environmental and Hydrogeological Processes in the Aral Sea Region: Analysis Based on Modern Technologies

- Analysis of hydrogeological processes in the Aral Sea region
- Application of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data technologies to environmental challenges
- Simulation and stochastic modeling of environmental and hydrogeological processes in the Aral region.

The event was conducted in a hybrid format with participation in English, Russian, and Uzbek. The conference provided a high-level platform for scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Suv xo‘jaligi obyektlaridagi suv resurslarini optimal boshqarish usulini aniqlashtirish

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada optimallikning zaruriy shartiga asoslangan asosiy optimallashtirish usullari, optimallik me‘zoni etib tanlangan qaralayotgan funksionalning boshqaruv variatsiyasining birinchi hosilasini yoki gradiyentini aniqlash masalasi qaralgan. Shuning bilan birga iste‘molchilarga suvni iqtisod qilgan holda yetkazib berish sharoitida suv xo‘jaligi obyektlaridagi suv resurslarini optimal taqsimlash masalasi optimalligining zaruriy shartida qo‘llaniladigan usullarning tahlili keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: optimallik me‘zoni, ko‘ndalang, bo‘ylama, variatsiya, Gradiyent usuli, maksimal, boshqaruv.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются основные методы оптимизации, основанные на необходимом условии оптимальности, а также задача определения первой производной или градиента управляющей вариации рассматриваемого функционала, выбранного в качестве критерия оптимальности. Одновременно представлен анализ методов, используемых в необходимом условии оптимальности задачи оптимального распределения водных ресурсов в водохозяйственных объектах в условиях экономического водоснабжения потребителей.

Ключевые слова: критерий оптимальности, поперечный, продольный, вариация, градиентный метод, максимум, управление.

Annotation. This article examines the main optimization methods based on the necessary optimality condition, as well as the problem of determining the first derivative or gradient of the control variation of the functional under consideration, selected as the optimality criterion. An analysis of the methods used in the necessary optimality condition for the problem of optimal water resource allocation in water management facilities under conditions of economical water supply to consumers is also presented.

Key words: optimality criterion, transverse, longitudinal, variation, gradient method, maximum, control.

Kirish. Masalaning asosiy maqsadi suv xo‘jaligi obyektlari hududida ko‘ndalang va bo‘ylama yo‘nalishlarda suv resurslari tezligining o‘zgarishini maksimal darajada oshirishdir:

$$I = \left(\int_0^T \int_0^L [u(x,t) - u^*(x,t)]^2 dxdt + \int_0^T \int_0^M [v(y,t) - v^*(y,t)]^2 dxdt \right) \rightarrow \max, \quad (1)$$

Quyidagi shartlarda

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l}
\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(uh)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(vh)}{\partial y} + i = 0, \\
\frac{\partial(uh)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(u^2h)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(uvh)}{\partial y} + g \frac{\partial(h^2/2)}{\partial x} = gh(S_{ax} - S_{fx}), \\
\frac{\partial(vh)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(v^2h)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(uvh)}{\partial x} + g \frac{\partial(h^2/2)}{\partial y} = gh(S_{ay} - S_{fy}). \\
U(x, y, t_0) = U_0(x, y), \quad (x, y) \in \Omega, \\
h_i(x, y, t) = H_i(t), \\
q_i(x, y, t) \cos \alpha + p_i(x, y, t) \sin \alpha = Q_i(t), \\
\alpha = (n, Ox), \quad (x, y) \in d\Omega_{\text{Ж}i} \quad i = 1, n_{\text{Ж}}
\end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

boshqaruv ta'siri ostida:

$$\begin{array}{l}
u(0, t) = u_1(t), \quad u(L, t) = u_2(t), \\
v(0, t) = v_1(t), \quad v(M, t) = v_2(t),
\end{array} \quad (3)$$

obyekt uchastkalarining ishlash rejimlariga cheklovlar quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$u_{\min} \leq u(x, t) \leq u_{\max}, \quad v_{\min} \leq v(y, t) \leq v_{\max}. \quad (4)$$

Optimallikning zaruriy sharti. Ko'rib chiqilayotgan (1)-(2) masala uchun cheklovlarning ichki sohasini boshqarishda optimallik me'zoni variatsiyasi quyidagi ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi.

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta I = & \int_0^L [u(x, T) - u^*] \delta u(x, T) dx + \int_0^M [v(x, T) - v^*] \delta v(x, T) dy - \\
& - \int_0^T \left\{ \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial u_1} \right)_{(L, t)} \right] \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial u_2(t)} \right) \right] \delta u_2(t) + \left[\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial u_1} \right)_{(0, t)} \right] \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial u_2(t)} \right) \delta u_1(t), \quad (1.40)
\end{aligned}$$

bu yerda $u = \lambda^1 S_{ay} + \lambda^2 S_{fy}$.

u gamiltonian hosilasini u_1 bo'yicha hisoblaymiz.

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial u_1} = gh\lambda^1 - gh\lambda^2 \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial u_2} = gh\lambda^1 - gh\lambda^2 \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial v_1} = gh\lambda^1 - gh\lambda^2 \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial v_2} = gh\lambda^1 - gh\lambda^2 \quad (8)$$

$\delta u_1(t), \delta u_2(t)$ boshqaruv variatsiyasidan funksional variatsiyalarining oshkor ifodalari aniqlandi. Ushbu variatsiyalar ixtiyoriy deb olingan va bu variatsiyalarda ifodalarning nolga tengligi optimallikning zaruriy sharti hisoblanadi.

Shunday qilib, Sen-Venan tenglamalari sistemasi uchun optimallikning yakuniy zaruriy shartlari, cheklovlarning ichki sohalari boshqaruvida quyidagi shaklga ega:

$$\left[gh\lambda^1 - gh\lambda^2 \right]_{x=0} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial u_1(t)} \right)_0 = 0, \quad (9)$$

$$\left[gh\lambda^1 - gh\lambda^2 \right]_{x=L} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial u_2(t)} \right)_0 = 0. \quad (10)$$

$$\left[gh\lambda^1 - gh\lambda^2 \right]_{y=0} \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial v_1(t)} \right)_0 = 0, \quad (11)$$

$$\left[gh\lambda^1 - gh\lambda^2 \right]_{y=M} \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial v_2(t)} \right)_0 = 0. \quad (12)$$

Tadqiqot usullari. Quyida iste'molchilarga suvni iqtisod qilgan holda yetkazib berish sharoitida suv xo'jaligi obyektlaridagi suv resurslarini optimal taqsimlash masalasi optimalligining zaruriy shartida qo'llaniladigan usullarning tahlilini keltiramiz.

Masalaning taqribiy yechimini olish uchun minimallashtirishning Gradiyent usuli qo'llaniladi.

$$I(u_m(t)) \rightarrow \min; \quad u_m(t) \in H, \quad (13)$$

bu yerda H – gilbert fazosi, minimallashtirish ketma-ketligini qurishga asoslangan. Ushbu ketma-ketlikni quyidagi ko'rinishda yozish mumkin:

$$u_{m+1}(t) = u_m(t) - \alpha_m I'(u_m(t)), t_0 \leq t \leq T, \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \quad (14)$$

bunda $u_0(t)$ – boshqaruv ta'sirining ma'lum bir boshlang'ich qiymati, α_m – musbat miqdor, I' – funksional gradiyenti, $u_m(t)$ ning ma'lum qiymati bo'yicha hisoblangan. Agar $I'(u_m(t)) \neq 0$, unda α_m ni $I(u_{m+1}(t)) < I(u_m(t))$ kabi tanlash mumkin.

Optimallik mezonining ikki marta differensiallanishi shartidan

$$I(u_{m+1}(t)) - I(u_m(t)) = \alpha_m (-\|I'(u_m(t))\|^2 + \theta(\alpha_m)) < 0 \quad (15)$$

ga ega bo'lamiz.

$\alpha_m > 0$ ning barcha yetarlicha kichik qiymatlarida, agar $I'(u_m(t)) \neq 0$ bo'lsa (14) jarayon masalaning berilgan aniqligi qanoatlantirilganda to'xtaydi va kerak bo'lganda $u_m(t)$ funksiya

harakatining boshqaruv atrofida optimal boshqaruvga tegishli bo'ladimi yoki yo'qligini aniqlash uchun qo'shimcha tadqiqotlar o'tkaziladi.

α_m qiymatni tanlashning turli usullari mavjud. Ulardan ba'zilarini keltirib o'tamiz:

1) α_m

$$f_m(\alpha_m) = \inf_{\alpha_m \geq 0} f_m(\alpha_m) = f_{m*}, \quad f_m(\alpha_m) = I(u_m(t) - \alpha_m I'(u_m(t))), \quad (16)$$

shartdan tanlanadi

Gradiyent usulining ushbu varianti *eng tez tushish* usuli deb ataladi.

(14) dan α_m qiymatini aniq aniqlash har doim ham mumkin emas, shuning uchun amalda (14) o'rniga quyidagi shartdan foydalaniladi.

$$f_{m*} \leq f_m(\alpha_m) = f_{m*} + \delta_m, \quad \delta_m \geq 0, \quad \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \delta_m \leq \infty, \quad (17)$$

yoki

$$f_{m*} \leq f_m(\alpha_m) = (1 - \lambda_m) f_m(0) + \lambda_m f_{m*}, \quad 0 < \lambda \leq \lambda_m \leq 1, \quad (18)$$

Bu yerda λ_m, δ_m kattaliklar (3.4) shartni bajarishdagi xatolikni tavsiflaydi.

2) $\alpha_m = \alpha > 0$ bo'sin, $I(u_{m+1}) < I(u_m)$ monotonlik sharti tekshiriladi va agar kerak bo'lsa, monotonlik sharti bajarilishini ta'minlash uchun α qiymat bo'laklanadi.

3) ba'zan α_m

$$0 < \varepsilon_0 \leq \alpha_m \leq 2/(L + 2\varepsilon), \quad (19)$$

shartlardan aniqlanadi. Bu yerda L – Lipshits doimiysi; $\varepsilon, \varepsilon_m$ – usulning parametrlari bo'lgan musbat sonlar.

4) α_m ni

$$I(u_m) - I(u_m - \alpha_m I'(u_m)) \geq \varepsilon \alpha_m \|I'(u_m)\|^2, \quad \varepsilon < 0 \quad (20)$$

shartdan tanlash mumkin. Xuddi shunday α_m ni aniqlash uchun odatda $\alpha_m = \alpha$ beriladi va yozilgan tengsizlik bajarilgunicha bo'laklanadi.

5) α_m qiymatlari uchun aprior vazifani quyidagi shartlardan belgilash mumkin:

$$\alpha_m > 0, \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \alpha_m = 0, \quad \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \alpha_m^2 < \infty \quad (21)$$

Masalan, $\alpha_m = c(k+1)^{-b}$, $c = \text{const} > 0$, $1/2 < b < 1$ deb olish mumkin. α_m ni bunday tanlovini amalga oshirish oson, lekin monotonlik shartlarini kafolatlamaydi va sekin yaqinlashadi.

6) agar $I_* = \inf I(u_m) > -\infty$, qiymat oldindan ma'lum bol'sa, α_m ni quyidagicha qabul qilish mumkin

$$\alpha_m = I(u_m(t)) - I_* / \|I'(u_m(t))\|^2. \quad (22)$$

Amalda, iteratsiya usullari har qanday shartlar ya'ni, hisobni tugatish me'zoni bajarilgunga qadar davom etadi,. Bu yerda hisobni tugatish me'zonlaridan

$$\|u_m(t) - u_{m+1}(t)\| \leq \varepsilon, \quad u, \quad |I(u_m(t)) - I(u_{m+1}(t))| \leq \delta, \quad u, \quad \|I'(u_m(t))\| \leq \gamma, \quad (23)$$

ham foydalanish mumkin, $\varepsilon, \delta, u, \gamma$ – berilgan sonlar. Ba'zan iteratsiyalar soni ko'rsatiladi.

Natijalar va ularning tahlili. Gradiyent proyeksiyasi usuli boshqaruv funksiyalariga cheklovlar o'rnatilganda masalani taqribiy yechish uchun qo'llaniladi:

$$u_m(t) \in U, \quad (24)$$

bu yerda U – gilbert H fazosidagi yopiq qavariq to'plam.

Gradiyent proyeksiyasi usuli asosida optimallashtirishning maksimalshiruvchi ketma-ketligi quyidagi qoidaga muvofiq quriladi:

$$u_{m+1}(t) = P_U(u_m(t) - \alpha_m I'(u_m(t))), t_0 \leq t \leq T, m = 0, 1, 2, \quad (25)$$

bunda P_U – boshqaruv sohasidagi loyihalash operatori.

$u_m(t)$ ning U to‘plamga proyeksiyasi quyidagicha aniqlanadi.

$$\|u_m(t) - w_m(t)\| = \sup \|u_m(t) - v_m(t)\|. \quad (26)$$

(26) ifoda shuni anglatadiki, agar hisoblangan boshqaruv qiymati U to‘plamga tegishli bo‘lsa, u holda hisoblangan boshqaruv qiymati qabul qilinadi. Agar hisoblangan boshqaruv qiymati U to‘plamga tegishli bo‘lmasa, u holda U to‘plamga yaqin qiymat olinadi. Bu usulni qo‘llash U cheklovlar to‘plamiga boshqaruvni proyeksiyalash formulasi mavjud bo‘lganda qulaydir.

Agar

$$U = \{u_m(t); u_{\min} \leq u_m(t) \leq u_{\max}\}, \quad (27)$$

bo‘lsa, u holda loyihalash operatori quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$u_{m+1}(t) = \begin{cases} u_{\min} & \text{npu } u_m(t) - \alpha_m I'(u_m(t)) < u_{\min}, \\ u_{\max} & \text{npu } u_{\min} \leq u_m(t) - \alpha_m I'(u_m(t)) \leq u_{\max}, \\ u_m(t) - \alpha_m I'(u_m(t)) & \text{npu } u_m(t) - \alpha_m I'(u_m(t)) > u_{\max}. \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

Masalaning berilgan aniqligi qanoatlantirilsa, kerak bo‘lganda $u_m(t)$ funksiya harakatining boshqaruv atrofida optimal boshqaruvga tegishli bo‘ladimi yoki yo‘qligini aniqlash uchun qo‘shimcha tadqiqotlar o‘tkaziladi.

Xulosa. Ushbu ishda qo‘llanilgan, optimallikning zaruriy shartiga asoslangan asosiy optimallashtirish usullari, optimallik me‘zoni etib tanlangan qaralayotgan funksionalning boshqaruv variatsiyasining birinchi hosilasini yoki gradiyentini aniqlashga asoslangan.

Suv xo‘jaligi obyektlaridagi suv taqsimotini optimal boshqarish masalalari uchun barcha optimallik me‘zonlari qavariq funksiyalar bo‘lganligi sababli, natijada olingan boshqaruvlar optimal boshqaruvga yaqin hisoblanadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati.

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